

NEWSLETTER

COMPAS_sCO₂

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NOVEMBER 25, 2022

Issue : IV

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. 958418

Team: 12 partners
from 7 countries

Research focus: New
particles, metal alloys
and heat exchanger

Duration: 1
November 2020 –
31 October 2024

Status of Implementation

Several results, deliverables, milestones have been achieved. All public deliverables and main activities are freely accessible through the project's website: <https://www.compassco2.eu/>. The section below summarizes the status of project activities by work package.

WP2 – DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF PARTICLES

After in depth analysis of two novel particle types made through different platforms, it was decided to focus on granulated particles as they were the most promising ones in terms of properties and cost. These granulated particles are present in their fourth generation after

significant improvements of their mechanical properties and heat capacity. The GEN4 particles are now sent around to three of the partners in order to have their surface modified via different techniques to reach even higher optical absorption values.

WP3 - DEVELOPMENT OF METALS

Novel Cr-NiAl alloys and Cr-Cr₃Si coating have been developed at University of Birmingham (UoB) and DFI-Dechema (Germany) with their microstructural characterisation and property evaluation ongoing. The Cr-NiAl alloys produced at UoB were compressed using a newly developed compression rig at DFI, c.f. the figure (left) below, to evaluate the strength from room temperature to 1000°C. Cr-Cr₃Si alloys were coated on the state-of-the-art materials using the slurry coating, c.f. the figure (right) below. Bridging the work package 3 and 4, bulk Cr-based alloys and the state-of-the-art materials coated with Cr-Cr₃Si will be delivered for environmental experiments in air/CO₂/sCO₂ and erosion experiments to measure the material degradation in end-application environment.

Experiments on novel Cr-based materials in DFI, Frankfurt: (left) newly developed hot-compression rig; (right) Michael Kerbstadt (DFI, left) and Thomas Blackburn (UoB) doing the slurry coating.

WP4 - EVALUATION AND MODELING OF METAL/MEDIUM INTERACTION

The work is ongoing to fully characterize the state-of-the-art materials in the heat exchanger aggressive environments (700-900°C, air/CO₂ and s-CO₂). CVR has completed the assembly of their s-CO₂ test system and is preparing their initial trials. CIEMAT and DFI are analyzing their initial sets of creep data at 700°C in air and CO₂, respectively. Long term exposures in CO₂ (CIEMAT) and air (FZJ) are providing insight into the microstructural changes and oxidation/carburization/nitridation mechanisms (figure below) that are occurring under these harsh conditions, supplying data for modeling (VTT) and leading towards a ranking of these state-of-the-art materials. As these state-of-the-art material test wrap up, the new material and coating tests are being planned in close cooperation with WP3.

Cross-sectional oxide scale morphology of Haynes 282 after 3,000h at 700°C. Haynes 282 appears to have a thicker oxide scale on average and more internal oxidation in CO₂ than in air, which agrees with the measured mass changes

WP5 – TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION

The particles “cold flow” was experimentally tested on prepared experimental rig for various tube bundle configurations (*left figure*). The gathered experimental data provided an insight into the flow of particular materials and revealed some helpful flow characteristics based on the tube bundle configuration parameters. Currently

the hot heater test is in preparation, where the particles will be heated up to 900°C. Knowledge from the “cold flow” experiments were applied here for the design of the heater section, to maximize the heat transfer. Furthermore the validated particle transportation system will be fabricated from suitable materials to withstand high temperatures (*right figure*).

Cold test - experimental setup and results

Hot heater test

Deliverables

D2.1: Particle optimization by surface treatment

November 3rd, 2022; Leader: CIEMAT

Four different techniques at three institutes were developed and tested on state-of-the-art and novel developed GEN3 particles. The initial

optical performance could be improved in all the cases. [Download](#).

D2.2: Particle optimization by modifying chemical composition

November 18th, 2022; Leader: SGREE

Different generations of fused and granulated particles with improved mechanical properties were developed by Saint-Gobain and proposed to the partners. The granulated particles GEN4 present the best compromise in terms of performance versus cost. [Download](#).

D3.1: Demonstration of New Cr aluminides and production as coupons for WP4 testing

November 3rd, 2022; Leader: UoB

Chromium-based superalloys are a desirable candidate material for the heat exchanger in the next generation of concentrated solar power (CSP). Chromium alloys appear to bear greater thermal stability over alternative high temperature materials such as nickel superalloys, cobalt superalloys and ferritic superalloys. Additionally, iron additions increase the hardness of the alloys and reduce age softening over their ternary alloy equivalent. Preliminary oxidation results show improved oxidation resistance of these alloys. [Download](#).

D3.2: Demonstration of New Cr silicides and production as coupons for WP4 testing

November 4th, 2022; Leader: DFI

Cr-Si-alloys with a two-phase microstructure consisting of a toughening bcc-Cr₂₃Si₆-matrix and strengthening, hard Al₃Cr₃Si precipitates are promising materials for use in oxidative high temperature environments. However, Cr-Si alloys have some drawbacks, which are currently excluding them from any structural applications. The focus of the conducted investigations is the microstructure evolution and the influence of Fe and Ni. To investigate the influence of Fe and Ni to the DBTT and mechanical properties, compression tests at different temperatures were carried out. [Download](#).

D7.4: Key Exploitable Results (KER) Table

October 31st, 2022; Leader: OME

In COMPASsCO₂, several results are being achieved. So far, 13 key exploitable results are being generated and classified based on different characteristics. In particular, the KERs are classified based on such information as results owners and contributors, result type, target audience, needs, result description, business sector/policy area, results maturity, current stage, competitors, value proposition, level of investment needed and services to third parties that result owners can provide.

Communication & dissemination activities

COMPASsCO₂ project featured at the European Health and Digital Executive Agency's (HaDEA) COP27 side event

Some of HaDEA's projects funded under Horizon 2020 that are developing solutions to address the challenges of making renewable energy generation and storage as sustainable as possible were presented at a side-event organized by the EU within the framework of COP27 in Sharm El-Sheikh on November 14th. Featured projects include new battery technologies, concentrated solar power, power-to-x and improved photovoltaics, for a total of 15 projects, including COMPASsCO₂. A [factsheet](#) was prepared by the EC Communication services, which briefly presents the projects.

Webinar on “novel high performance materials and components,” November 15th, 2022

In collaboration with other EU H2020 projects such as HIPERMAT, ACHIEF, topAM and CEM-WAVE, **COMPASsCO2** takes part in the webinar on “novel high performance materials and components” held on November 15th from 10h00 to 12h00 (GMT+2). [COMPASsCO2 presentation](#) was on “novel Cr-based alloys strengthened by intermetallics for structural

and coating applications at high-temperatures >800°C.” The presentation was delivered by Kan Ma (UoB) and Mathias Galetz (DFI). The event was attended by 73 stakeholders. [Watch the video!](#)

Free webinar

Novel high performance materials & components

November

15th

Zoom platform

ASTEP Design Workshop organized, October 20th, 2022

In collaboration with several projects, including ASTEP, SHHIP-CO2, Soltermin, SCARABEUS PROJECT, SWS-heating, and FRIENDSHIP, COMPASsCO2 took part in a workshop on “ASTEP system design” organized by ASTEP on October 20th, 2022, to discuss synergies and explore joint communication and dissemination activities. The [presentation](#) was delivered by Daniel Benitez (DLR).

Webinar on “Supercritical CO2 R&D in Europe” September 22nd, 2022

In collaboration with other EU H2020 and nationally funded projects such as Carbosola, CO2OLHEAT, DESOLINATION, SCARABEUS, sCO2-Efekt, sCO2-for-NPP and sCO2OL Projects, **COMPASsCO2** took part in a new webinar series on “**R&D activities on sCO2 in different applications in Europe.**” The first webinar was an introductory event during which each project presented its own objectives & expected impacts, scope, main results/outcomes, and options for further exploitation. The COMPASsCO2 presentation

was given by Daniel Benitez (DLR). The event was attended by 131 stakeholders. All the proceedings (video and presentations) can be downloaded [here](#).

The second episode will take place on December 5th from 14h00 to 15h00 (CEST) and will focus on “**components challenge: compressors development in sCO2 cycles.**” [Registration!](#)

Webinar speakers

COMPASsCO2 presentation at ACHEMA Conference, August 23rd, 2022

COMPASsCO2 results were presented at ACHEMA Conference 2022, held in Frankfurt on August 23rd, 2022. The presentation discussed: the heat exchanger as the key component for efficient heat transfer; the development of new materials and efficient

particles for CSP plants; and testing of particles, metals and CO2 interaction. The [presentation](#) was delivered by Michael Kerbstadt (DFI).

COMPASsCO2 results presented at Processes4Planet Forum, June 9th, 2022

COMPASsCO2 results were presented at the Processes4Planet Forum, held in Brussels on June 9th, 2022, mainly: power plant operation conditions, solar receiver and field optimization, heat exchanger conceptual design and sCO2 Brayton power block; state of the art proppants and new developed particles (granulated and

fused particles); metals for the heat exchanger tubes; particles, metals and sCO2 interaction; and heat exchanger pilot test. The [presentation](#) was delivered by Maxime Rouzès (CMI).

COMPASsCO2 results presented at SolarPACES 2022

September 27-30, 2022
Albuquerque, NM, USA

28th SolarPACES Conference

Poster on *“Optimization of Spinel Absorber Coatings for CSP Particle Receivers”*

The poster presented the solid particles, different particles treated with coatings developed in COMPASsCO2 as potential candidates to be used as receiver and storage in CSP plants to increase their operating temperature and efficiency. The Poster was presented by Gema San Vicente Domingo (CIEMAT).

Oral Presentation on *“Round Robin Test of Absorptance and Emittance of Particles for CSP”*.

The presentation summarized the Round Robin Test (RRT) measuring absorptance and emittance and which was conducted on five different particle types with 16 different measurement devices among seven partner institutes. In addition, the successful conduction of this RRT has led to publication of a [SolarPACES guideline](#) detailing the measurement process, calibration procedure and window correction method (if applicable) for spectrophotometers, FTIRs and handheld devices. The oral presentation was delivered by Florian Sutter (DLR).

Journal Article - “Improved Performance of Ceramic Solar Absorber Coated with Black Oxide Pigment

Journal article on *“Improved Performance of Ceramic Solar Absorber Particles Coated with Black Oxide Pigment Deposited by Resonant Acoustic Mixing and Reaction Sintering,”* was

Article
Improved Performance of Ceramic Solar Absorber Particles Coated with Black Oxide Pigment Deposited by Resonant Acoustic Mixing and Reaction Sintering

published in Coatings Journal on May 31st, 2022.

A deep-black Cu, Mn, Fe- pigment with a spinel structure was employed to coat standard proppants in order to improve long term solar absorptance. Coated bauxite proppants exhibit a significantly improved, long-term stable solar

absorption accompanied by a promising abrasion resistance. The presented coating methodology is considered to be scalable to industrial production.

The article was developed by Gözde Alkan, Peter Mechnich and Johannes Pernpeintner (DLR).

Meetings

Fourth General Assembly Meeting – The 4th project meeting will take place from November 29th to December 1st, 2022 in Almeria, Spain. This will be the first physical GA meeting since the inception of COMPASsCO₂. It will discuss the overall progress, on-going activities, challenges, and next steps. A technical visit to both Plataforma Solar de Almeria (PSA) and Andasol-3 plant will take place.

Technical Committee Meeting – The TCM was held on May 25th to discuss the main challenges, internal coordination among the

different WPs and any risks and mitigation measures.

Quarterly Phone Conference Meetings: The Quarterly phone call took place on August 23rd, 2022. It discussed the key results and inputs for the different work-packages and any problems/delays/deviations.

Dedicated WP Meetings – Several dedicated WP meetings were organized to discuss the technical aspects of the project with involved partners.

How to get involved in COMPASsCO₂ activities

Become a member of the project's stakeholders' network

Whether you want to learn more about specific WP activities, collaborate with the consortium or act as an external expert, kindly contact us at contact@compassco2.eu. We will keep you updated about project activities, invite you to attend the project's public events and ask your feedback on the progress and main outcomes of the project.

Check our website and follow us on social media networks

LinkedIn

<https://www.compassco2.eu/>

THANK YOU

For more information

Check the project's website: www.compassco2.eu

Contact us: contact@compassco2.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action (RIA) under grant agreement No. 958418.